

Mixed-ligand complex equilibria of Cu^{II} with histidine and guanylurea

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Abstract : Combined pH-metric and spectrophotometric investigations on the mixed-ligand complex formation of Cu^{II} with histidine [H₃⁺N-CH(-CH₂C₃H₃N₂)-COO⁻, hereafter, hisH[±]] and guanylurea [H₂N¹C(=O)N²HC(=N³H)N⁴H₂, hereafter, GuH] in aqueous solution (ionic strength, 0.1 mol dm⁻³) at 25°C indicated the complexes : [Cu(hism)⁺], [Cu(hism-H)], [Cu(hism)(Gu)], [Cu(hism-H)(Gu)⁻], and [Cu(hism-H)(Gu-H)²⁻]; where, hism⁻ stands for -COOH deprotonated bidentate *histamine-like* (NH₂, N³-imidazole) chelating histidinate mono anion, his-H²⁻ stands for both -COOH and imidazole N¹H deprotonated histidinate dianion, Gu⁻ stands for =N³H deprotonated guanylurea mono anion and Gu-H²⁻ stands for both =N³H and H₂N¹/N⁴H deprotonated guanylurea dianion. Formation constants of the proton-ligand and metal-ligand complexes were evaluated by mathematical modeling of the complex formation equilibria using computer based method. Varied modes of coordination of histidine and guanylurea to Cu^{II} involving interesting structural equilibria were established from the shifts of the electronic spectral absorption maxima of copper-histidine-guanylurea mixtures with change of pH of the solution.

Keywords : Copper, histidine, guanylurea, mixed-ligand complex equilibria.

Introduction

In majority of copper proteins, copper atoms are coordinated by one or more of the histidine imidazole-N atoms^{1,2}. Histidine, shows ambidentism in its modes of coordination to copper³⁻⁵. Due to imidazole-N coordination, histidine, among all the natural amino acids, shows highest binding affinity for Cu^{II} (log β₂ ~ 18.3)³ and histidine bonded Cu^{II} can even discriminate between σ-basic and π-acidic ligands in ternary complexes⁶. Depending upon pH and metal to ligand ratio in the solution, histidine may coordinate Cu^{II} as a (N,N) bidentate *histamine-like* ligand (hism⁻), using the amino-N and imidazole-N atoms (mode-a), as a (N,O⁻) bidentate *glycine-like* ligand (gly⁻), using the amino-N and carboxylate-O atoms (mode-b), and also as a (N,N,O⁻) tridentate *histidine-like* ligand (his⁻), using the amino-N, imidazole-N and carboxylate-O atoms (mode-c). Two of these three donor atoms in mode-c coordinate two equatorial positions on the copper coordination geometry and the third donor atom coordinates from an apical position. Barring

the mode-b, the other two modes of coordination with a dominance of the mode-a have been observed for some binary and ternary complexes of Cu^{II} with histidine as a ligand⁵⁻¹². Therefore, although extensively studied, Cu^{II}-histidine complex equilibria deserved further investigation. With a view to elucidate the modes of coordination of histidine (hisH[±]) to Cu^{II} in presence of strongly coordinating (O,N) and/or (N,N) bidentate ligand, guanylurea, [H₂N¹C(=O)N²HC(=N³H)N⁴H₂, GuH], mixed-ligand complex equilibria of Cu^{II} with histidine, and GuH have been investigated by combined pH-metric and spectrophotometric measurements in aqueous solution at 25 ± 1°C at a fixed ionic strength, I = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (NaNO₃).

Formation constants of the most probable complexes (Table 1) were evaluated by the mathematical modeling of the pH-titration data (Fig. 1) with the aid of the computer program, SCOGS¹³. Modes of coordination of the ligands were elucidated from the shifts of the electronic spectral absorption maxima of the metal-ligand mixtures

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Table 1. Stoichiometry of Cu^{II}-histidine-guanyurea complexes and refined values of the proton-ligand and metal-ligand binary and ternary constants

SI no	Complex species	<i>p</i>	<i>q</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>s</i>	log β _{<i>pqr</i>s}
1.	[H ₂ hisH [±]] ²⁺	0	1	0	-3	16 72
2.	[HhisH [±]] ⁺	0	1	0	-2	15 12
3.	[hisH [±]]	0	0	1	-1	9 10
4.	[HGuh ⁺]	0	0	1	-2	10 20
5.	[GuH]	0	0	1	-1	8 20
6.	[Cu(OH) ⁺]	1	0	0	1	-6 29
7.	[Cu(OH) ₂]	1	0	0	2	-13 05
8.	[Cu(hism) ⁺]	1	1	0	0	10 21
9.	[Cu(hism-H)]	1	1	0	1	4 18
10.	[Cu(hism) ₂]	1	2	0	0	20 12
11.	[Cu(hism)(gly)]	1	2	0	0	19 73
12.	[Cu(hism)(hism-H) ⁻]	1	2	0	1	13 00
13.	[Cu(hism-H) ₂ ²⁻]	1	2	0	2	7 45
14.	[Cu(Gu) ⁺]	1	0	1	0	5 61
15.	[Cu(Gu)(OH)]	1	0	1	1	-0 24
16.	[Cu(hism)(Gu)]	1	0	1	0	16 38
	Δlog K _{Cu(16)}					(+0 56)
17.	[Cu(hism)(Gu)(-H) ⁻]	1	1	1	1	7 95
18.	[Cu(hism)(Gu)(-2H) ²⁻]	1	1	1	2	-1 74

Abbreviations hism⁻ = -COOH deprotonated bidentate *histamine-like* (NH₂, N³-imidazole) chelating histidinate mono anion, his-H²⁻ = both -COOH and imidazole N¹H deprotonated histidinate dianion, gly⁻ = *glycine-like* (NH₂, -COO⁻) coordination by histidine, Gu⁻ = N³H deprotonated guanyurea mono anion and Gu-H²⁻ = both N³H and H₂N¹/N⁴H deprotonated guanyurea dianion

Fig. 1. Representative pH titration curves of Cu^{II} guanyurea histidine system 1, 0 005 (M) HNO₃, 2, (1) + 0 001 (M) (HGuh)⁺, 3, (1) + 0 001 (M) (H₂hisH[±])²⁺, 4, (2) + 0 001 (M) Cu^{II}, 5, (3) + 0 001 (M) Cu^{II}, 6, (5) + 0 001 (M) (HGuh)⁺, initial volume = 0 025 dm³, titrant = 0 1 (M) NaOH, ionic strength, I = 0 1 (M) NaNO₃, (M = mol dm⁻³)

(Fig. 2) and the complex formation equilibria were elucidated from analysis of the speciation curves (Figs 3–4) In view of identification of histidine and some of its metal derivatives as Alzheimer’s Aβ-channel blockers¹⁴ and application of guanyurea and its N,N’-di-substituted derivatives in bioremediation of soils polluted by spilt oil and chemical pollutants¹⁵, the results of the present equilibrium study may provide useful clues to the molecular mechanism of their drug actions.

Fig. 2. Electronic spectra of 1:1:1 Cu^{II} histidine guanyurea mixture at different pH, ionic strength, I = 0 1 mol dm⁻³ (NaNO₃) Curve (pH) a (3), b (4.75), c (5), d (6), e (7) f (8), g (9), h (10) and i (11)

Results and discussion

(a) Proton-ligand equilibria :

(i) Protonation-deprotonation equilibria of histidine

In dilute acidic solution (pH ≤ 2), histidine (hisH[±]) exists in its di-protonated (H₂hisH[±])²⁺ form, in which the added protons remain associated with the imidazole-N³ atom and amino-N atom. The carboxylic acid group remains partly ionized (pK_{H3} ~ 1.60). Above pH ~ 3, the zwitterionic (H₂his[±])⁺ is the dominant species (Fig. 3). The imidazolium (³NH⁺) proton is lost above pH 5 (pK_{H2} ~ 6.02) and the aminium proton (-NH₃⁺) is lost above pH 8 (pK_{H1} ~ 9.10)¹². Due to tautomerism within the imidazole ring, the N¹H hydrogen atom in hisH[±] and his⁻ ions may alternate between ¹N and ³N atoms¹⁶

(ii) Protonation-deprotonation equilibria of guanyurea^{17,18,b,d} :

In dilute acidic solution (pH ~ 2), guanyurea (GuH)

Fig. 3. Speciation curves of (a) 1 : 1 and (b) 1 : 5 Cu^{II} : histidine systems : 1, [H₂hisH[±]]²⁺; 2, (HhisH[±])⁺; 3, (hisH[±]); 6, Cu(OH)⁺; 7, Cu(OH)₂; 8, Cu(hism)⁺; 9, Cu(hism-H); 10, Cu(hism)₂; 11, Cu(hism)(gly); 12, Cu(hism)(hism-H)⁻; 13, Cu(hism-H)₂²⁻; FM = Free Cu^{II}, FB1 = Free his⁻.

occurs in its monoprotonated (HGuh⁺) form. With rise of pH, it offer two well separated buffer regions (pH < 4) and (7 < pH < 9), due to successive deprotonation of either N¹H₃⁺ (or N⁴H₃⁺) (pK^H ~ 2.0) and N³H (pK^H ~ 8.20) moieties to form the mono anion, Gu⁻.

(b) Binary Cu^{II}-ligand equilibria :

(i) Cu^{II} : histidine equilibria¹² :

Complex formation of Cu^{II} with histidine in the 1 : 1 binary system starts at pH ~ 3, where the ligand exists mostly in its [HhisH[±]]⁺ form and the hydroxo species, viz., Cu(OH)⁺, Cu(OH)₂ are totally absent (Fig. 3a).

The 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : histidine complex (8) (Table 1) is the major copper containing species in the pH range 3–8, with a concentration maxima (~80%) at pH ~ 5–5.5. Two possible modes of bidentate chelation by the histidinate ion, viz., *histamine-like* coordination (hism⁻) using the amino-N atom and the imidazole-N atoms (mode-a) and *glycine-like* coordination (gly⁻) using the amino N-atom and the carboxylate-O atom (mode-b) give two

structural possibilities, (8a) and (8b) respectively for the complex (8).

Cu^{II} in these two isomeric structures tends to take up two molecules of solvent H₂O to achieve its preferred 4-coordinated square planar geometry :

Electronic spectral absorption maxima (λ_{max}) of Cu^{II} corresponding to these two structures may be estimated applying eq. (1)¹⁶ :

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{\text{max}} \text{ (nm)} = & 10^3/[0.294 (\text{C=O}/\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{OH}/=\text{NH}) \\ & + 0.346 (\text{COO}^-) + 0.434 (\text{N-imz}) \\ & + 0.46 (\text{NH}_2) + 0.494 (= \text{N}^-)] \quad (1) \end{aligned}$$

where, the groups in the parentheses represent the number of such coordinating groups (total not exceeding 4) and the numerical coefficients are their ligand field contributions in μm^{-1} . Estimated λ_{max} values for structure (8a) and (8b) are 675 nm and 733 nm respectively. The experimental λ_{max} value (693 nm) of 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : histidine mixture at pH ~ 5–5.5 at which the concentration of complex (8) passes through a maximum (Fig. 3a), is closer to the estimated λ_{max} value corresponding to structure (8a). Slightly higher experimental λ_{max} value (by ~18 nm) suggests intermolecular apical carboxylate coordination. The alternative structure (8b) with *glycine-like* chelation (mode-b) may be discarded, because of wide difference of the calculated λ_{max} corresponding to this structure from the experimental value. As the speciation curves (Figs. 3a) imply, formation of the complex (8) may be described according to the eqm. (2) :

Another buffer region corresponding to the release of one mole of H⁺ per mole of Cu²⁺ is observed between pH 6–8 with a blue shift of the λ_{max} (~by ≥ 20 nm) to 656 nm around pH 6.5–7 (Fig. 2). This buffer region can not be due to deprotonation of a coordinated H₂O molecule to OH⁻ ion within the complex (8a), since H₂O and OH⁻ are very closely placed in the spectrochemical series. The only possible source of this buffer action is release of the imidazole (N¹H \rightleftharpoons N³H) proton from (8a), producing the complex [Cu(hism-H)] (9) according to the eqm. (3) :

The pK^H (8) value (~ 6.03) corresponding to this deprotonation (eqm. 3) :

$$pK^H = \log \beta_{1101} - \log \beta_{1100} \quad (3a)$$

reflects the enhancement of acidity of otherwise neutral histidine imidazole $-N^1H$ due to coordination of the tertiary N-atom of the imidazole ring to Cu^{II} . Ligand field contribution of deprotonated histidine-imidazole N^3 atom to Cu^{II} comes around $\sim 0.48 \mu m^{-1}$ and $\sim 0.52 \mu m^{-1}$ respectively, in the presence and in the absence of apical carboxylate coordination. Complex formation in 1 : 5 Cu^{II} : histidine system commences around pH 2.5 (Fig. 3b) with appearance of the 1 : 1 complex (8) (eqm. 2), showing a concentration maximum ($\sim 30\%$) at pH $\sim 3.5-4$, where the imidazole N^1H deprotonated 1 : 1 complex (9) does not occur at all. The major Cu^{II} containing species above pH 4 is the 1 : 2 Cu^{II} : histidine complex, which may exist in two isomeric structures, viz., $[Cu(hism)_2]$ (10), involving *histamine-histamine-like* coordination by the two his^- ligands and $[Cu(hism)(gly)]$ (11) involving *mixed-histamine-like glycine-like* (modes-*a, b*) coordination by the two histidinate ligands¹². The uncoordinated carboxylate-O and imidazole-N atoms in structures (10) and (11), however, can provide apical coordination to Cu^{II} intermolecularly. Inclusion of structures involving only *glycine-like* chelation (mode-*b*) viz., $Cu(gly)^+$ and $Cu(gly)_2$, for the 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 Cu^{II} : histidine complexes respectively, in the calculation of stability constants, gives higher values of standard deviations, therefore, such species are not considered.

The speciation curves (Fig. 3b) of 1 : 5 copper : histidine system show almost equal % of free Cu^{2+} ion, the 1 : 1 complex $[Cu(hism)^+]$ (8a) and two forms of the 1 : 2 complex, viz., $[Cu(hism)_2]$ (10) and $[Cu(hism)(gly)]$ (11) remain in equilibrium at pH $\sim 3.5-4$.

The estimated average of the λ_{max} value (*ca.* 662 nm) of these species [eq. (1)] is close to the experimental value (654 nm) of 1 : 5 Cu^{II} : histidine mixture at this pH (~ 4). A small blue shift (~ 27 nm) to 617 nm, with rise of pH to ~ 5 , suggests transformation of (11) to (10) in increasing proportions with rise of pH. Since all these three types of complex species, (8a), (10) and (11) occur simultaneously, the initial stages of complex formation in the 1 : 5 Cu^{II} : histidine system may be described according to eqm. (4) and (5) preceded by eqm. (2), as the speciation curves (Fig. 3b) imply :

A red shift of the λ_{max} value to 636–642 nm with rise of pH (above 6) is indicative of apical coordination of Cu^{II} by carboxylate-O atom and or by uncoordinated imidazole-N atom in the complexes (10) and (11), which pass through their respective concentration maxima ($\sim 55-60\%$) and (40–45%) around pH 5.5–6. Above pH 6, both (10) and (11) disappear simultaneously with building up of concentration of the imidazole deprotonated complexes, $[Cu(hism)(hism-H)^-]$ (12) and $[Cu(hism-H)_2^{2-}]$ (13). Finally above pH 8, (12) is transformed to (13) (Scheme 1) :

Scheme 1

Although small, but a definite final blue shift of the λ_{max} value by $\sim 5-6$ nm is observed above pH 9, as increasing proportions of (12) and (13) appear in the solution through deprotonation of coordinated imidazole in (10) and (11) (Scheme 1).

(ii) 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : *guanylylurea equilibria*^{18b,d} :

Complex formation of Cu^{II} with *guanylylurea* in binary 1 : 1 metal : ligand system starts around pH ≥ 4 , at which the metal ion exists as $Cu^{2+}(aq)$, $Cu(OH)^+(aq)$ and the ligand exists as the electroneutral GuH species. $[Cu(Gu)^+(aq)]$ (14) and $[Cu(Gu)(OH)]$ (15) complexes appear simultaneously^{18b,d}. Above pH ~ 5.5 , the complex (14) is transformed to the ternary hydroxo complex (15), through deprotonation ($pK^H \sim 5.85$) of a coordinated H_2O molecule (Scheme 2) :

Scheme 2

The complex (15) dominates the entire pH range above pH 7. Unlike the analogous 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : biguanide system^{18a,c} in which biguanide =N²H, (or =N⁴H) deprotonated complex, [Cu(Bg-H)(OH)], dominates above pH 7, no such guanylurea deprotonated complex is indicated. Guanylurea (Gu⁻) ion may coordinate in three bidentate modes (CO, =N⁻), (NH₂, =N⁻), (=NH, =N⁻) giving three isomeric structures (14a), (14b), and (14c) (Scheme 3) for the 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : Gu⁻ complex [Cu(Gu)(H₂O)₂]⁺ (14).

Scheme 3

The complex, (14) occurs in the pH range 4–10 and deprotonates to (15) through structure (14c). On the other hand, deprotonation equilibria of the 1 : 2 Cu^{II} : guanylurea complex, [Cu(Gu)₂] and mixed ligand, Cu(Gu)(L) complexes^{18b,c}, where, L = glycinate⁻ and glycyglycinate⁻ involve release of proton (s) from the coordinated Gu⁻ ion (Scheme 4) :

Scheme 4

Electronic spectral λ_{\max} of Cu^{II}-Gu⁻ mixture is expected to show blue shift on deprotonation, due to stronger ligand field provided by deprotonated amide-N atom than the amide carbonyl O-atom. No such blue shift is of course expected for the second step deprotonation, which involves the loss of a proton from an uncoordinated OH group.

(c) 1 : 1 : 1 Ternary Cu^{II} : histidine : guanylurea equilibria :

Complex formation in the 1 : 1 : 1 ternary Cu^{II} : histidine : guanylurea system starts around pH 3 with appearance (eqm. 2) of the 1 : 1 binary Cu^{II} : histidine complex, [Cu(hism)⁺] (8), which passes through its concentration maximum (~60%) at pH ~5. Above this pH the complex (8) along with the ligand GuH disappear (Fig. 4) with concomitant appearance of the imidazole

Fig. 4. Speciation curves of (a) 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : guanylurea and (b) 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : histidine : guanylurea system : 1, (H₂hisH[±])²⁺; 2, (H₂his[±])⁺; 3, Hhis[±]; 4, (HGuH)⁺; 5, HGu; 6, Cu(OH)⁺; 7, Cu(OH)₂; 8, Cu(hism)⁺; 9, Cu(hism-H); 14, Cu(Gu)⁺; 15, Cu(Gu)(OH); 16, Cu(hism)(Gu); 17, Cu(hism)(Gu)(-H)⁻; 18, Cu(hism)(Gu)(-2H)²⁻; FM = Free Cu^{II}, FB2 = Free Gu⁻.

N¹H deprotonated complex, [Cu(hism-H)] (9) (eqm. 4) and the ternary complex, [Cu(hism)(Gu)] (16) (eqm. 6) :

pK^H (8) value of ~ 6.03 (eq. 3a) gives a measure of enhancement of acidity of the imidazole N^1H of histidine due to coordination of its N^3 -atom to Cu^{II} . Since, guanyurea anion (Gu^-) may coordinate Cu^{II} in the binary complex (14) in three different bidentate modes (14a,b,c), using its ($O=C$), ($=N^-$) and ($-NH_2$) groups, it gives rise to three possible structures (16a, 16b and 16c) for the ternary complex (16) (Scheme 5) :

Estimated electronic spectral λ_{max} values^{16,18} for a

Scheme 5

square planar geometry of Cu^{II} in the complex (16), represented by the structures (16a), (16b) and (16c) are 595, 595 and 541 nm respectively. Experimental λ_{max} value (650–652 nm) of 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{2+} : histidine : guanyurea mixture; at pH ~ 7 (Fig. 2), at which the complex (16) makes $\sim 70\%$ of total Cu^{II} and passes through its concentration maximum, is closer to the estimated λ_{max} values for the structures (16a) and (16b). Red shift of ~ 55 nm of the experimental λ_{max} value may be due to intermolecular apical carboxylate coordination¹⁶. Thus, the ternary complex (16) is best described by the two isomeric structures, (16a) and (16b). The third structure (16c) may be discarded, as the estimated λ_{max} value (541 nm) corresponding to this structure is much lower than the experimental value. The mixed ligand complex (16) passes through its concentration maximum ($\sim 70\%$) at pH ~ 7 , whereas, the imidazole deprotonated 1 : 1 complex (9) occurs to the extent of 30–35% in a wider pH range (6–10). Above pH 7, (16) disappears with release of two moles of H^+ per mole of Cu^{II} , and concomitant appearance of two deprotonated ternary complexes :

$[Cu(hism)(Gu)(-H)]$ (17) and $[Cu(hism)(Gu)(-2H)]$ (18) (Scheme 6) :

Scheme 6

However, the above deprotonation equilibria (Scheme 6) are not as simple as they appear. Loss of the first proton from the imidazole NH moiety of either (16a) or (16b) produces $[Cu(hism-H)(Gu)^-]$ (17a), which may exist in two isomeric structures :

(17a₁) $[Cu(hism-H)(=N^-) \curvearrowright (OCNH_2)^-]$ and

(17a₂) $[Cu(hism-H)(=N^-) \curvearrowright (HN=COH)^-]$,

where, the symbol, \curvearrowright , means bidentate chelation (Scheme 7). On the other hand, loss of the first proton from the coordinated Gu^- ion of (16a) or (16b) may pro-

Scheme 7

duce another isomer of (17), $[Cu(hism)(Gu-H)^-]$ (17b), which may also exist in two isomeric structures :

(17b₁) $[Cu(hism)(=N^-) \curvearrowright (O-C=NH)^-]$ and

(17b₂) $[Cu(hism)(=N^-) \curvearrowright (N^--COH)^-]$.

While loss of the second proton from (17a₁) and (17a₂)

can take place only in one way, i.e. through deprotonation of the coordinated guanylurea anion, producing the complex, [Cu(hism-H)(Gu-H)²⁻] (18a), which may be described by two isomeric structures :

loss of the second proton from (17b₁) and (17b₂) can take place in two different ways, viz., deprotonation of the imidazole NH of coordinated histidinate ion, producing (18a₂) and or deprotonation of the uncoordinated (=NH) or (-OH) group of metal bound (Gu-H)²⁻ ion producing (18b), [Cu(hism)(Gu-2H)²⁻] i.e., [Cu(hism)(=N⁻)C(O⁻=N⁻)²⁻], or, [Cu(hism)(=N⁻)(N⁻CO⁻)²⁻].

Estimated λ_{max} values of square planar Cu^{II} complexes^{16,18} having structures (9), (16a), (16b) (17a₁), (17a₂), (17b₁) and (18a₁) are 654, 595, 595, 579, 579, 577 and 562 nm and those for such complexes having structures (17b₂), (18a₂) and (18b) are 531, 531 and 519 nm respectively. Estimated average λ_{max} value (609 nm) (Fig. 2) of equal proportions (~30%) of the complexes (9), (16) and (17, described by the structures 17a₁ and 17a₂), occurring around pH ~8.5 is quite close to the observed λ_{max} value (~609–617 nm) of 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : histidine : guanylurea mixture adjusted to this pH. This suggests involvement of the structures (16a), (16b), (17a₁), (17a₂) and (17b₁) in the first step deprotonation equilibria of the ternary complex (16) with exclusion of the structure described by (17b₂). Similarly, the concordance of the estimated average λ_{max} value (598 nm) of the complexes (9), (17) and (18a, described by 18a₁) with the experimental λ_{max} value (~598–601 nm) of 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : histidine : guanylurea mixture at pH ≥10, where the complex (18) is the major (~70%) copper containing species, along with the complexes (9) and (17), suggests the involvement of the structure (18a₁) in the second step deprotonation of (16), thereby discarding the structures (18a₂) and (18b), for which the estimated λ_{max} value (519 nm and 531 nm respectively) are much lower than the experimental value at this pH. Thus, excluding the structures (17b₂), (18a₂) and (18b), the two step deprotonation equilibria of the ternary complex (16) may be described according to (Scheme 8) :

Scheme 8

Experimental

Materials and methods :

All the reagents were of AR grades and their solutions were prepared in double distilled CO₂ free water. Procedures for standardization of the reagents, pH metric and spectrophotometric measurements, evaluation of the equilibrium constants using the computer program SCOGS¹³ were same as described in our earlier communications^{12,18}. For determination of proton-ligand and metal-ligand constants, a series of solutions, each of initial volume 0.025 dm³, containing known amounts (0.005 mol dm⁻³) of free HNO₃, known amounts (0.001–0.002 mol dm⁻³) of the ligands, viz., histidine and guanylurea in their protonated forms (H₂hisH[±])²⁺ and (HGuh⁺) respectively, in the absence and in the presence of known amounts (0.0002–0.001 mol dm⁻³) of Cu^{II} nitrate were pH-metrically titrated with a carbonate free standard 0.1 mol dm⁻³ NaOH

solution, maintaining a fixed ionic strength, 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (NaNO₃) at 25 ± 1°C (thermostated).

Some representative pH titration curves are presented in Fig. 1.

Calculation of formation constants :

The overall formation constant (β_{pqrs}) of a homo metallic generalized ternary complex species, [Cu_p(his)_q(Gu)_r(OH)_s], (Table 1) may be defined according to,

$$\beta_{pqrs} = \frac{[\text{Cu}_p(\text{his})_q(\text{Gu})_r(\text{OH})_s]}{[\text{Cu}]^p[\text{his}]^q[\text{Gu}]^r[\text{OH}]^s} \quad (7a)$$

The stoichiometric members, p , q and r may be positive or zero, s is a negative integer for a protonated species such as (H₂hisH[±])²⁺, (H₂his[±])⁺, GuH₂⁺, GuH, a positive integer for a hydroxo or a deprotonated species like Cu(OH)⁺, Cu(Bg-H)⁺, Cu(his-H) and zero for a normal species such as Cu(Gu)⁺, Cu(his)⁺, Cu(his)(Gu) etc. For 1 : 1 and 1 : 5 binary Cu^{II} : ligand systems, $p = 1$ and the value of q and r depend upon the molar ratios of metal : ligand in the solution. For 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : hisH[±] : GuH system, $p = q = r = 1$. Since the pH range of some of the complex formation equilibria were overlapping with the hydrolytic equilibria of Cu^{II} (aq) ion, formation of binary as well as ternary hydroxo complexes were considered in calculating the stability constants (β_{pqrs}) of the metal-ligand complexes, however, pH-titration data (Fig. 1) prior to the commencement of any turbidity were subjected to calculation.

For the histidine ligand (his⁻), bidentate (NH₂, N³-imidazole) i.e., *histamine-like* (mode-a) and (NH₂, COO⁻), i.e., *glycine-like* (mode-b) along with mixed *histamine-like glycine-like* chelation were considered, but inclusion of complexes with only *glycine-like* chelation gave larger values of standard deviations. So, such species were excluded from the calculation. Complex formation equilibria were elucidated by analyzing the speciation curves (Figs. 3 and 4) and the modes of coordination of the ligands were established from the shifts of electronic spectral absorption maximum of Cu^{II} in binary and ternary systems (Fig. 2) with change of pH of the solution^{16,18}.

Conclusions :

Histamine-like bidentate (NH₂, N-imz) chelation of Cu^{II} prevails in 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : histidine complexes, [Cu(hism)⁺] and [Cu(hism-H)] in the pH range (3–10), with intermolecular apical coordination by the carboxylate-O and or uncoordinated N-imz atom (where, imz = imidazole ring). On the other hand, the 1 : 2 Cu^{II} : histidine complex exists as structural isomers composed of *histamine-histamine-like* (NH₂, N-imz) chelated [Cu(hism)₂] and mixed *histamine-like glycine-like* [(NH₂, N-imz) (NH₂, COO⁻)] chelated [Cu(hism)(gly)], with the former slightly dominating (~60%) over the latter (~45%) in the pH range 5–6. With rise of pH, the mixed isomer is transformed to the *histamine-histamine-like* isomer, [Cu(hism)₂], which loses its imidazole ring NH proton at still higher pH (≥ 9). Cu^{II} : histidine complexes with structures involving only *glycine-like* chelation by histidine are totally absent in the equilibrium.

Histamine-like chelation also prevails in 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : histidine : guanylurea ternary complexes. The imidazole deprotonated *histamine-like* chelated 1 : 1 complex, [Cu(hism-H)] (~25%), and the ternary complex [Cu(hism)(Gu)] (~65%), are the dominant copper containing species in the pH range of biological significance. With rise of pH above 8, both these complexes are transformed to, [C(hism-H)(Gu)] and [Cu(hism)(Gu-H)] and at still higher pH both complexes are transformed to [Cu(hism-H)(Gu-H)]. Although guanylurea is structurally similar to biguanide and mixed-ligand Cu^{II}-histidine-guanylurea complexes exist in isomeric equilibria like the corresponding Cu^{II}-histidine-biguanide complexes¹², even to greater degree of flexibility, but basicity of coordinated guanylurea is not as strong as that of biguanide, so as to displace the bound histidinate ion from the ternary complexes in basic medium.

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